

SOME ASPECTS OF CAESALPINIA GILLIESII AND DAVID'S BUDDLEIA (BUDDLEIA DAVIDII), BREEDING TECHNOLOGY

Mamadaliyeva Sobira Bahodir kizi

Doctoral student of Tashkent State Agrarian University

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Abstract. *Caesalpinia* or peacock flower (lat. *Caesalpinia*) is a small tree, an erect or creeping shrub, the shoots of which are often thorny. The genus belongs to the Legume family and has about 150 species. Habitats include Uruguay, Argentina, Barbados, tropical America and southeast Asia. In general, the peacock flower can be found in warm regions of the northern and southern hemispheres. In central Russia it is grown at home.

Keywords: *caesalpinia, breeding, technology, method.*

Introduction. As a rule, among them there are small trees, perennial shrubs up to three meters high, and vines, the stems of which are often covered with thorns. The trunk, branches and leaf petioles are covered with small thorns, and the leaves themselves are delicate, small, bipinnate, compound-fingered, up to 20 cm long, with many small oval leaves. They resemble acacia, but the structure is a little more complex and even somehow more orderly. The entire crown is arranged in layers, airily and gracefully, but at the same time it seems lush, massive and spreading, like that of conifers. The ability of the soft green leaf segments to fold closer to night and straighten out again in the morning gives the bushes additional charm. In hot climates, *caesalpinia* remains evergreen, but if cold weather sets in, it sheds its leaves.

Materials and methods. *Caesalpinia Gillis* blooms all summer with large yellow flowers with long red stamens. The flowers are 5-8 cm in diameter, with five corrugated petals, and 10 embossed and long crimson stamens protruding beyond the corolla, collected in pyramidal inflorescences up to 40 cm long, consisting of 30-40 flowers. The flowers have a light, pleasant aroma. In tropical climates, flowering continues almost all year, and in cooler regions the plant rests in winter. Plants grown from seeds are ready to flower in 2-3 years. The brightness and delicate aroma of flowers attract butterflies, bees, and in the natural environment also hummingbirds.

Results and discussion. The flowers are so beautiful that *caesalpinia* is given different colorful names like “peacock flower”, “parrot bush” or “bird of paradise”, although in its homeland in Argentina the name is so-so: “goatee”, apparently, with enough imagination, the hanging stamens can be likened to it.

As a result of pollination, fruits appear - pods with beans. The pod is flat or slightly swollen, the surface is leathery. It remains intact or bursts and the beans scatter to the sides, due to which reproduction occurs in nature.

The seeds - beans - ripen in large pods. When the beans are ripe, the pod dries out and at some point opens with a click, scattering the beans over a long distance. These beans are poisonous to people, there is no need to try them. By the way, it's also better not to put flowers in your mouth. Pets should be kept away from it, as the bush is poisonous to cats and dogs.

Caesalpinia Gillis or *Gillis* is one of the most beautiful plants, widely cultivated in countries with warm climates. In the city of Tashkent, *caesalpinia* was cultivated in 2016. In early August 2021, yellow flowers with long pink stamens and unripe bean-shaped fruits were found on the plants. The leaves are small, bipinnate, green. The height of the bush reached 1 m in height.

Caesalpinia is a relatively easy plant to grow, easy to prune, can be used as a hedge, trained to live in a large patio pot, or grown in open ground. Trees in the wild are often covered with orchids and other epiphytes.

Winter hardiness of the plant. The culture is thermophilic and suitable for growing in open ground only in southern territories. There the plant remains green almost all year round, and with the help of pruning it takes on the appearance of a tree. Under the influence of temperatures of 4-6°C with a minus sign, the leaves are already crumbling. If the mark drops below -6-8°C, the above-ground part will begin to die off.

Reproduction of caesalpinia. The plant is propagated by semi-lignified cuttings and seeds. Cuttings are used apical after spring pruning. Root in a mixture of sand and peat, covered with plastic film and moderately moistening the soil mixture. If the non-lignified part of the cutting is buried in the soil, as a rule, rotting occurs.

A fairly common method of propagating caesalpinia is by seed. Beans are purchased in stores or obtained from cultivated plants through artificial pollination. They are collected as they ripen, before the pod cracks, otherwise the seeds scatter a considerable distance from the mother bush.

On the eve of germination, the beans are subjected to scarification - slight damage to the shell using a file or other sharp object, as well as soaking in warm water for 24 hours. The seeds are buried in a loose peat-sand mixture no more than half a centimeter. Cover with a plastic bag and keep at a temperature of approximately 24-25 degrees Celsius. Shoots appear quite quickly, first forming simple cotyledon leaves, and then complex pinnate leaves. Specimens grown from seeds bloom, depending on maintenance conditions, after a period of six months to 3 years.

Caesalpinia gilliesii has a high growth rate and can bloom within 10 months from sowing the seeds. If it grows in the fresh air, then its flowering is more luxuriant. Inflorescences are formed from flowers of a bright sunny yellow hue. The plant is not afraid of drafts and can grow even in the shade. Caesalpinia peacock flower grows actively throughout the year. The lighting level needed is bright but diffuse. It is important to provide 8 hours of daylight.

Air temperature. During the spring-summer period, a moderately warm temperature regime is optimal: 21-25°C. From autumn to spring, maintain the temperature between 15-18°C. Adult plants are more drought tolerant, but young caesalpinias can be destroyed by drying out the earthen coma. Lack of moisture often causes a lack of flowering or the dropping of existing buds. So, during the warm season, water every 2-3 days, focusing on the drying of the top layer of soil. As it gets colder, we reduce watering; it is permissible to dry a clod of earth to half its depth.

Conclusion. Although the parrot bush adapts to dry indoor air, it is better to maintain humidity at at least 50%. To do this, periodically spray the bushes with warm water from a fine spray. In winter, move the flower pot away from heating systems and appliances. It is advisable to take the pride of Barbados out into the fresh air in the summer, i.e. place on the balcony, veranda, garden. Don't forget about proper lighting levels, as direct sunlight can cause burns.

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